

Post-Covid-19 Education Management Strategies

Nuray Hürata

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Abstract

The era of the New Normal, also known as the World of Distortion, is discussed; up to this point, the world has evolved into the Next Normal. The transition to the Next Normal poses significant challenges for higher education institutions, particularly their administrators, faculty and students. The most important thing is to strike a balance between living your life and learning new things. We live in a time when everything is changing rapidly and there is no time to be ready for it. Emerging challenges have had an impact, particularly on the education front. The use of technology is critical to solving the problem. In addition to children, managers, trainers and other members of the teaching staff will also need to change. To meet the proficiency requirements, students must be able to demonstrate high-order thinking skills, the capacity to analyze situations, and creative thinking. More importantly, in the field of education, corporate managers play a role similar to that of supreme leaders, guiding everyone else towards the achievement of a common goal. Ministry of Health officials mentioned this, referring to the forecast that the infection case may be high in the new year (Bangkokpost, 2021). Impact of COVID-19 on Higher Education According to MacIntosh 2020, the ongoing coronavirus outbreak is creating "a massive wave of disruption in the higher education sector." As a result of the spread of the virus, it has had a significant impact on higher education all over the world. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a devastating impact on many areas, including the economy, education, public health, local

livelihoods in both urban and rural settings, and the functioning of society. Among all of them there is a deterioration in the usual methods of communication. As a direct result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the education system has faced a serious hurdle, such as the restriction on offline learning and the number of lecturers available. In order to bring the social distance to the desired level, the training was held in online discussion forums and classrooms. Online classes can be accessed using various virtual platforms such as Zoom, Google Classroom, or software that is accessible to everyone. These platforms have shown significant benefits in the context of Thailand's education system. As a result, it is important for students to understand how to leverage digital technology as the new online education platform.

Keywords: *Covid – 19, Educational Management, Post-Covid-19 Educational Management, New Era in Educational Management Strategies*

Introduction

The beginning of the pandemic crisis triggered issues in a wide variety of the educational system's subsystems. As the first phase of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis began to abate, various sectors initiated conversations regarding the "New Normal." For instance, how are we going to make sure that the learning that takes place throughout the COVID-19 timeframe is indeed useful? In light of this, what sorts of skills and fields of study need the new training model to cover? Will individuals be able to learn more as a result of the use of technology, or will it make inequality worse? Is it true that we might look at this conundrum as a chance for us to gain knowledge?

The COVID-19 crisis is a test of the great need for educational administration, which must modify its way of thinking in line with the New Normal that is taking place in accordance with the "New Abnormal" that is impacting education. Educational institutions are able to withstand this test, since it is a test of the great need for educational administration. This is due to the fact that the crisis serves as a test of the significant requirements placed on educational administration, which requires a shift in mentality. The calamitous nature of the change that is now taking place cannot be overstated. Because of the world's volatility, unpredictability, complexity, and ambiguity, educators and other education employees are forced to undergo personal growth and development. They are constantly willing to gain new knowledge and open to taking on new challenges, which enables them to conquer any difficulty that may occur and discover answers. I. Volume 8 Number 2 (May–August 2565).

They have an insatiable thirst for knowledge and are constantly willing to take on new challenges. As a consequence of this, students who graduate from these programs are equipped with the ability to acquire skills that are suitable to the requirements of society in the 21st century. This enables educators, administrators, and other education personnel to bring about a paradigm shift in educational administration, with a specific emphasis on the expansion of self-induction during this time period. As a consequence of this, educators and other members of the education staff need to prepare themselves to operate as members of the government in order to effectively administer education throughout the time of the New Normal (Krisada Sektrakul,2020).

Methodology

The article on the impact of COVID 19 on education shows both good and negative effects and they are summarized as follows: (Krisada Sektrakul,2020)

1. *1. The hybrid model of education that combines time-honored in-person instruction with flexible, remote employment is becoming more popular. In the past, individuals were unable to acquire their education anywhere else except in conventional classrooms, but in the future, they will be more receptive to the concept of blended learning. It utilizes a wide range of diverse pedagogical techniques all at once. Because of this, the student does not attend each and every class; nonetheless, they are still able to make progress in their educational experience. This shift will gradually become more socially acceptable as both teachers and students grow acclimated to the new method of instruction made possible by the online learning platform model of educational technology.*
2. *2. In general, the degree of growth and development may be recognized in general. It is vital to have a good knowledge that it is not enough to study subjects from a number of areas in order to participate in interdisciplinary learning. To be able to create a new connection that will ultimately result in the development of a novel invention, you need to be able to link many domains in some way.*
3. *3. It is intended to expand the amount of collaboration in the area of education in order to boost both the efficiency and effectiveness of the operation. Beyond the confines of any specific educational institution, more cooperation between teachers, material developers, and others will take place.*

For instance, online learning systems may assist share qualified and experienced teachers in a subject area with other institutions. Additionally, online learning systems can help exchange information to save time when building new courses. In addition, several minds are able to converse with one another and exchange their own areas of knowledge.

An increase in the amount of labor required of instructors and essential improvements for schools. The amount of competence that instructors possess as well as their level of familiarity with online education both need to be improved. Learners have to be taken into consideration throughout any stage of the process that involves the development of technologically-based curriculum or instructional materials.

The job of teachers shifts to become more of facilitators for the students, and the students themselves are now accountable for learning with the assistance of their teachers. Students are able to think critically as a consequence. Because of this, the most essential problem is figuring out how to alter the mentality or perspective of trainers who are working in the same direction.

Literature Examples

The decline in the amount of knowledge retained has an effect on the growth of the available human resources. Even if there is an alternative in the form of online tutoring, it is not as beneficial as studying in conventional classrooms since there is no connection between instructors and students, and students also do not have the chance to engage with their fellow classmates. There are several subfields of academic inquiry that almost exclusively need practical experience. The decrease in learning may also have an effect on the fundamental essential knowledge that is required for the development of human capital in a community. It is evident that many nations are making the issue worse by increasing the number of technological devices that are present in educational settings in an attempt to provide students with more access to educational possibilities. With regard to educational institutions, there has been a notable decline in the earnings of private educational institutions, particularly those that do not get support from international students or from the present economic situation. As a consequence, parent wages have fallen as a direct result of this trend. As a consequence of this, a great number of educational institutions are experiencing financial problems, which has led to the suspension or cancellation

of the course. This is a totally unique occurrence that has never taken place in the history of the world.

As a consequence, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought about outcomes that may be seen in either a favorable or bad light, depending on one's perspective. The crisis presented an opportunity to take on more duties, which unlocked previously closed doors. Given the tremendous shift in circumstances, the managers of higher education institutions need to either find other jobs or upgrade their skills. As a result, they are going to need to come up with new things, such as new methods of instruction, a new way of doing things at work, a new society, and a new environment. From this point forward, this will become a new way of life while taking place inside the context of an educational institution.

Education in a World of Interruptions

At this time, we live in a world that is rapidly deteriorating and experiencing a great deal of unpredictability. The outbreak of COVID-19 (COVID-19), advancements in technology that have an influence on society, and changes in the world's economic and social situations are a few instances of these shifts. It has been through such a dramatic change in response to the way the world is right now that it is now considered to be the norm. At times, we refer to it as the "New Normal," and other times, we call it the "VUCA world." It is of the utmost importance that the heads and leaders of organizations provide assistance for the expansion of the country in a well-planned manner. When the globe is thrown into turmoil, educational institutions are compelled to retain their focus on the years to come. Even educational institutions have been impacted by the vast changes that the age has brought about, and as a result, the original educational administration may no longer be enough to satisfy the requirements of today's ever-evolving globe. These shifts have left their mark on every aspect of life.

It is likely that conventional educational programs that have been around for a very long time would be unable to adapt to the changes that are occurring. According to Phornvit Phacharintanakul (2019), managers of educational institutions of all sorts need to be proactive in their awareness of the difficulties that are presented by the fact that certain job-related knowledge and skills are no longer in demand. This awareness must focus on the challenges that are provided by the fact that certain job-related knowledge and skills are no longer in demand. After that, applications using information technology are developed to support the administration of the learning process. Aside from analytical thinking, synthesis, creative problem solving, and the

ability to educate oneself, abilities in information technology are the most significant skill in modern education. These skills are vital for today's learning and are the most important skill in contemporary education.

According to Wichai Wongyai and Marut Patphol's (2019) research, this coincides with the conclusions that they obtained. "Today's education competes not only with current achievements or talents, but also by anticipating the future and preparing for future events," according to the management of educational institution managers. Because of this, additional personnel has to be trained not just to accept new technology into institutions but also to supply knowledge to those institutions.

Students should be able to demonstrate higher-level thinking abilities, including the capacity to analyze situations and think creatively as competences. The following difficulties were identified as a result of study conducted by Supattarasak Khumsamart, Sirintip Kuljittree, and Kowit Juntapala (2020), as stated in their conclusion.

1. In order to go forward, organizations need to adopt a new attitude or viewpoint. To begin, organizations need to construct a corpus of knowledge by seeing the world through a "lens of opinion." After that, individuals need to look for new experiences while keeping an open mind in order to be receptive to new points of view, ways of thinking, and the results of the new lens. After making the necessary adjustments to their mentality, they will be able to lead their companies into a fresh and less restrictive commercial dimension.

2. Information will become available when it has "Faster Performance," which will make it possible for us to locate flaws more quickly than companies that have sluggish performance. They worry about making errors, which means that the slower companies operate, the more experience they have in dealing with and fixing the sluggish issue. This implies that the slower organizations run, the more experience they have.

3. The struggle known as "Learning from Mistakes" is an essential one. Even the most efficient organizations may not make significant headway. One of the reasons for this is that companies have previously made a mistake, but in the process of trying to develop something new, they have learnt from the incorrect perspective. If businesses continue to make errors while having access to solutions, they will be forced to deal with issues and become hurdles that will slow down progress and, eventually, learning.

4. The only way to ensure that the body of knowledge is maintained is to ensure that learning is ongoing. In order to develop a continuous learning system and base their achievements on it, businesses need to have both a "Learning Attitude" and "Appropriate Learning Methods" in place. At long last, companies may compete on an equal footing with major organizations in the future of driving the Thai economy. All of the problems that have been outlined are important factors to consider while developing the New Normal schooling. It is a design for adaptation or future training programs, stressing the conception or belief of employees who will have to modify and develop the power of self-improvement. It is a blueprint.

Argument

The concept of having a "growth mindset" emphasizes the significance of duties and positions. If administrators are aware of the obstacles, they will be better able to manage educational institutions so that they can meet the needs of the present scenario and achieve educational development.

Next Normal Education

Following the completion of the New Normal, it will be ready to proceed with the New Normal. It is a style of thinking, learning, communicating, implementing, and managing that makes life easier for those who are prepared to undergo change. A cashless society, a vending system, home delivery services, technology for shopping with actual experiences like virtual reality, and working from home are examples of such shifts. These will carry over into the Next Normal and continue to be protected. Students of all levels will inevitably get some portion of their education online at some point. The transition to the Next Normal in higher education will be exceedingly difficult for university administrators, faculty members, and students alike. The most essential component is striking a healthy balance between everyday living and innovative pedagogy.

The training is delivered through an online medium; however, just because this is how it is delivered does not indicate that it is the most efficient way of instruction. The quality of education has not suffered in any way, despite the fact that fewer students are opting to get their education in the conventional classroom environment. Importantly, the curriculum should be connected across the many areas of academic study, and the knowledge that is offered in the various areas of

academic study should not be duplicated; nevertheless, they should be presented in a manner that is more interdisciplinary. As a consequence of this, the general populace will be better equipped to contribute as responsible global citizens in society. It is feasible to get to the conclusion that the issue that needs to be addressed is the transition from the "New Normal," which reflects a new way of life that can coexist with COVID-19, to the "New Normal," which expresses the life that will exist after COVID-19. This is the problem that needs to be addressed. Planning and adjusting are essential tasks, particularly in the process of incorporating newly developed technology and digital services.

It includes online platforms that fulfill the needs for convenience while placing a focus on safety, cleanliness, and the influence on the environment. The following is a list of trends that are associated with living in the manner of the Next Normal:

- 1. The Stay-at-Home Economy: As a result of the COVID-19 challenge, people from all over the globe have altered the way they spend their life. The home, in addition to being used as a place of dwelling, has been converted into a setting that is suitable for a broad range of activities.*
- 2. When people start living in the period of the Next Normal with the Contactless Society, their primary worries will be related to hygiene and safety. As a direct consequence of this, technology has been developed to lessen the negative effects of exposure; 3. In the world of Next Normal, concerns about public health and the natural environment will play an important role.*

Management Education and Training As a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, a number of educational institutions have been forced to close their doors, which is the primary reason why the educational experience of more than 90 percent of all students throughout the globe is being badly affected. It is needed that the COVID-19 Situation administration Center (CCSA) waive any school facilities or educational institutions for the administration of classrooms, both online and offline. The implementation of the Blended Learning method will occur, or students may be given the opportunity to study from the comfort of their own homes, depending on the degree to which it is suitable and pertinent for each individual school or educational institution.

since a consequence of this, administrators of educational institutions need to do research on educational management strategies, since the New Normal includes essential processes that

must direct and lead the administration of learning. The management of instructional models, the education of educators for the contemporary world, and the administration of lessons, which involves listening to feedback from educators, parents, students, and the community are all required for this. Patcharaporn Duangchurn (2020) carried extensive study and compiled significant suggestions about the modification of educational management procedures from the point of view of educational institutions and educators. The following is a list of the additional recommendations that will assist administrators in gaining ideas in the administration of educational institutions in the numerous disciplines that are detailed below:

- 1. The principle of social distancing is strictly adhered to in classroom teaching in order to maintain the distance and cleanliness of students from one another. 1. The 100% online learning strategy is suitable for educational institutions that are preparing to implement teaching and learning management systems alongside online courses. 2. Online learning is suitable for educational institutions that are preparing to implement teaching and learning management systems alongside online courses.*
- 2. Students engage in both online and traditional classroom instruction as part of blended learning; 4. "homeschooling" refers to the practice of instructing children in their own homes. Importantly, the emphasis is on developing effective interactive online learning by engaging students with virtual instructors, which is believed to be an improvement over conventional classroom learning.*

As a direct consequence of this decision, the test will henceforth be referred to as the "Assessment for Learning" rather than the "Learning Assessment." The purpose of this evaluation is to determine how effectively students are matched to the different teaching pedagogies and skill sets that their instructors need of them. Because of this, the process of assessment in the New Normal places a greater emphasis on comprehension as opposed to decision making (Marut Pattaphol, 2020).

The following are some of the ways in which the concept of teacher role regulation and teacher development was presented in order to illustrate the adaptation of education that took place throughout the New Normal period:

1. *During the New Normal era, he portrayed the educational system in a harmonious light. To take the place of conventional trainers in their capacities as learning facilitators or supports. There is a common notion that many educated educators who possess the traits of a facilitator are capable of integrating lessons, teaching strategies, and evaluation of learning in order to assist development. This idea stems from the fact that there are a large number of qualified educators who possess these characteristics.*
2. *Providing training to teachers so that they may become learning advocates is one method to alter the way that learning is administered, which will ultimately benefit students. As a result, the curriculum for teaching and learning need to be varied, and the manner of instruction ought to be modified so that it incorporates both conventional and digital teaching strategies. As a consequence of this, the structure of the course has to take into consideration the many attributes that are associated with the pupils. For instance, there are several examinations developed for a variety of reasons, and in addition to this, students and lecturers work together to establish the environment of the classroom (Siridej Kasuprom, 2020). In addition, the Office of the Basic Education Commission (OBEC) has presented the concept that education in this day and age should find a point to develop Thai children into the digital world or 21st century education by building a teaching and learning curriculum that would be a competency-based curriculum. This proposal was put up in light of the fact that education in this era should find a point to develop Thai children into the digital world or 21st century education. This idea was presented with the purpose that education in this era should find a point to grow Thai students toward the digital world or 21st century education. This was the motivation behind the introduction of this concept. According to Wichai Wongyai's research from 2020, it will make it possible for more youngsters in Thailand to realize their full potential. I Volume 8 Number 2 (May-August 2022) I 287 8 2 (-2565) Additionally, Supattarasak Khumsamart, Sirintip Kuljittree, and Kowit Juntapala (2020) assert that corporate managers have to take into consideration the following dimensions.*
3. *Relevant educational institutions should concentrate on learning in the past, in the present, and in the future as part of the Transformation in Education initiative. When moving toward becoming an expanding learning organization, one of the key aims of learning should be to improve the amount of cooperation it has with the community as well as other organizations in the outside world. This may be accomplished through connecting with the community.*

4. *In view of the fast advancement of technology, I would like to bring to your attention the fact that communication in both directions may take place through computer. As a result, customers have a right to know how to use it properly and whether or not it is appropriate for various practical purposes.*
3. *Teaching: In this new era of education, the information that is being taught should be posted on the internet so that others may freely access the Massive Open online Courses (MOOCS) and connect with educators by contributing their skills in order to generate new content as a place. This should be accomplished through MOOCs, which stands for "massively open online courses."*

The technological environment and the material it produces will be traded, taught, and eventually published on the web. This paradigm shift is seen as an asset in the process of developing the advantages of institutions into leadership positions in terms of the dissemination of knowledge through the internet world. This pandemic situation involving COVID-19 is an important opportunity to manage education in accordance with the New Normal method, a significant change in the concept that should be consistent and connected with student learning by adjusting the curriculum to be compatible with the COVID-19 situation. The New Normal path is an important concept change that should be consistent and linked to student learning by adjusting the curriculum to be in line with the COVID-19 situation. According to this crisis, which we call "collapse", an important and unexpected change is taking place in every aspect of life. As a result of the disruption, new learning models are created and these models have both more creative and more inclusive interactions. The development of new technologies is very important and plays a fundamental role. By using the program or by performing a web search, students will gain a significant portion of the knowledge and skills they want from that location.

Instructors have a responsibility to be prepared for unexpected challenges. Curriculum teaching techniques need to be redesigned by teachers based on a flexible approach to accommodate diverse student demographics. It is important to recognize that education has the potential to become the new normal. It is important that educational institutions have collaborated with a wide range of sectors, including the public and commercial sectors, to research instructional management systems.

Institutional Managers in Teaching

Institution managers have a high level of quality in implementing the education management process efficiently and effectively to keep up with the situation in the era of disruptive change.

This can be achieved by the following methods:

- 1. They have a favorable attitude toward digital technology and recognize that it impacts management in a variety of fields and that they themselves should serve as a good example of how to use technology. The administration of academics, the management of teaching and learning, the management of human resources, the management of buildings and the environment, the management of student affairs, and the development of relations with the local community are all managed via the use of technology. Throughout all of an educational institution's operations, a database management system that has been developed specifically for use in educational settings should be used. According to Ekachai Keesukphan (2016), corporate managers need to be able to determine the suitable and acceptable usage of social media platforms such as LINE, Facebook, Twitter, WeChat, and Instagram for their businesses. This is essential for the operation of the school administration in order for it to be successful.*
- 2. They need to educate themselves on the most recent digital and communication technologies in order to stay up with the quick rate at which technological advancement is occurring.*
- 3. It is their responsibility to formulate the organization's vision, strategies, and directives in a way that is consistent with the objectives that have been established. They have no choice but to become destructive themselves in order to lead in such a horrible society.*
- 4. They need to manage the infrastructure in order to get the most out of it, which includes the hardware, the software, the networks, and the wireless networks. Because of this, both the instructors and the students may easily access it whenever it is most convenient for them.*
- 5. It is their duty to establish in educational institutions a culture of work and an atmosphere that are receptive to the proliferation of digital technology and communication technology.*
- 6. People who work in educational institutions are expected to participate in regular training in order to acquire the knowledge and abilities essential to function successfully with digital technology and communication technology.*

7. *It is their job to encourage, assist, and inspire the teaching staff, as well as the staff members who come up with innovative ideas for the teaching administration or the running of the school. 289 ปีที่ 8 ฉบับที่ 2 (พฤษภาคม - 2565) I Vol 8 No.2 (May-August 2022)*
8. *It is their job to provide educators and other members of the staff and students who work in educational institutions with monitoring and consultation systems on the usage of communication technology and digital technology.*
9. *Management must have management skills such as knowledge and expertise in all areas of management, resource management skills including problem solving techniques and strategic tactics, and conceptual thinking skills in critical, analytical, and synthetic thinking (Patcharaporn Duangchuen, 2020). Management must also have conceptual thinking skills in order to be successful. For them to be successful in their work, having talents such as these is very necessary. The Techsauce Team (2018), which developed the conclusion of the Digital Disruption Leaders Qualifications from the Forbes Global CEO Conference 2018, has compiled a summary of the qualifications, and it may be seen below.*

Leaders are responsible for instilling an entrepreneurial mindset in their teams;

- *It is important for leaders to choose the most compatible collaborators;*
- *Company leaders need to reorganize tasks that need to be completed;*
- *To create an “Inclusive Culture”, also known as an open culture within the company, leaders must demonstrate an attitude of openness;*
- *Quick adaptation is required for leaders; And*

Additionally, Techsauce (2018) offers:

- *Leaders should form teams full of 'Believers'.*
- *Visionary leadership is necessary for leaders as well as for the development of values. Leaders must be market oriented and market oriented;*
- *The "right person to work with" should be determined by the leaders;*
- *It is up to the leaders of the organization to ensure that "empowerment" is achieved; And*

- *Ultimately, leaders are responsible for providing the appropriate tools for change and ensuring that key performance indicators align with goals. In conclusion, the current COVID-19 dilemma presents an important opportunity for education in the context of the New Normal.*

This constitutes a significant change in the idea that should be maintained throughout the educational experience of children and should be relevant to it. It is advised that the curriculum be put into practice by adapting it so that it fits the COVID-19 situation, interacting with everyone who has an interest in the matter, increasing the amount of flexibility in the study period, and using various learning styles. In this age of disruption, the administrators of educational institutions need to have a certain attitude, set a good example for others, be knowledgeable about communication technologies and digital technologies, and have the ability to direct, encourage, support, and motivate the personnel working in educational institutions in order to keep up with the change. In addition to this, they are obligated to provide supportive supervision, follow-up, and consultation services, as well as ways to problem-solving that are the result of management expertise. This material may be found in the May-August 2022 issue of the Western University Research Journal of Humanities and Social Science, Volume 8, Issue 2. Executives at corporations are tasked with the duty of navigating their companies successfully through the plethora of difficulties that may arise. They are accountable for bringing about changes in management practices and directing educational institutions in the direction of accomplishing the objectives that have been established. They require in-depth analysis at the level of learning management in order to satisfy the learning needs of students, to prepare students to develop professions, and to guarantee that students continually grow rather than being disrupted by every change. As a consequence of this, the management of educational institutions on the basis of the New Normal requires administrators to adapt the school administration to change according to the context of the time and situation as well as the circumstances. First, they need to place their attention on the advantages that will be bestowed onto direct stakeholders such as pupils, teachers, support personnel, and parents. They are required to use all of their talents, exhibit excellent leadership, and be armed with ideas, concepts, and theories pertaining to management that can be applied to a wide variety of situations. In addition to this, they need to be ready to steer everyone to victory and finally make it through this crisis without any adverse effects being felt by the organizations or ideologists that work for them. It is abundantly obvious that the shift from the "New Normal" to the "New Normal" is connected to digital changes such as online learning, in addition to advancements in technology

and digital innovation, which people of all ages and walks of life need to learn and utilize in their day-to-day lives. Nevertheless, a different paradigm may be discovered in the new way of living that is becoming prevalent in the period of the Next Normal. The majority of people have come to terms with the reality of the situation and are prepared to make changes to their way of life as a direct consequence of it. This is done to guarantee compliance with the new laws that have been formed on the basis of surviving the pandemic, which may remain in people for a very long period and cause them to get used to endemic illnesses. When it comes to the subject of education, it is feasible to make the forecast that the mode of educational communication will develop into a mode of online instruction at some point in the future. One of the advantages of doing this is that it will lower the probability that people would spread germs to one another.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Even though the COVID-19 issue has been resolved, it is anticipated that the movement toward education that is given via digital platforms such as online learning will continue to gain momentum. It's possible that the only path ahead is for us to adjust to the contemporary world and acknowledge that the manner of life our forefathers had is not possible in the present world. Corporate managers may be likened to supreme leaders in the sense that they are responsible for directing everyone towards the accomplishment of a shared objective. As a consequence, these managers are required to be exceptional transformational leaders in the area of education. The capacity to successfully navigate unfamiliar circumstances is an essential component of leadership acumen. Both a sector of academic study and a practical activity, educational administration focuses on the operation of educational institutions. Educational administration may be seen of as both an academic and a practical endeavor. Because it draws from a variety of fields, including sociology, specialized sciences, politics, economics, and general management, the study of education does not have a definition that is widely recognized by the academic community. According to Bush (2011), educational administration should pay particular attention to the goals and aspirations of the educational system. The basis for integrating schools' activities and task management goals is still highly significant, despite the fact that they are the topic of several disagreements and conflicts. These criteria provide invaluable aid to educational institutions and enable management to evaluate whether or not the school is capable of achieving certain educational goals. There is always the risk of falling into "bad management" if the connection between purpose and management is not clearly established. This risk cannot be eliminated. An "emphasis on procedures at the expense of goals and educational values" is one of the defining

characteristics of this approach. There are many different models of education administration, and some of these models focus on the aims of the institution, while others highlight the goals of the person. In the middle is a series of graphic insights from people who believe that "corporate" objectives may be more successful than individual goals in certain circumstances.

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